

ALKALI-ACTIVATED MATERIALS FOR LUNAR ISRU: FORMULATION DESIGN, MULTI-SCALE CHARACTERIZATION, AND IDENTIFICATION OF NOVEL ITALIAN REGOLITH SIMULANTS. F. Santoro de Vico ¹, H. Amiri ², A. Driouich ¹, G. Melchiori ¹, M. Massironi ^{1,3}, L. Valentini ³. Affiliation: ¹ CISAS Centre for Space Research (francesco.santoro@unipd.it), University of Padua, Italy; ² Department of Earth Sciences, Utrecht University, The Netherlands; ³ Department of Geosciences, University of Padua, Italy

The development of sustainable construction materials for lunar settlements is a key challenge for In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) strategies. Alkali-activated materials (AAMs) represent a promising route for lunar construction, as they can be produced from local regolith with minimal Earth-transported components and at relatively low processing temperatures. Within the GLAMS project, we present a comprehensive approach spanning from formulation optimization using commercial lunar regolith simulants to the identification and validation of novel Italian simulant sources.

AAM formulations were optimized through a Design of Experiments (DoE) approach on commercial simulants, investigating key parameters including alkaline activator type (NaOH, KOH, sodium silicate), activator dosage, metakaolin addition, and curing temperature. Urea was also explored as an additive to modify rheological properties and enhance mechanical performance. Optimized formulations were then produced under three distinct curing conditions relevant to lunar surface operations: standard atmospheric curing, vacuum curing, and 3D printing.

The resulting specimens were fully characterized chemically and also here we will present the data by high-resolution X-ray microtomography (micro-CT) at Utrecht University (The Netherlands), at 6 μm voxel resolution. Three-dimensional image analysis using Dragonfly and pyPore3D software enabled quantitative assessment of porosity distribution, pore connectivity, tortuosity, and vesicle geometry across all three curing regimes. This comparative microstructural investigation provides critical insight into how processing conditions influence pore network architecture and, consequently, material performance under ISRU-relevant scenarios.

Building on these results, within the SPACE IT UP project, recent work has identified pyroclastic deposits from Mount Etna (Cisternazza pit crater) as compositionally analogous to Apollo 14 regolith samples [1], establishing them as validated novel Italian lunar simulants. The transfer of optimized formulations from commercial to these newly characterized simulants represents the next step toward locally sourced, geologically grounded ISRU research. This integrated approach, from formulation design to 3D microstructural characterization to simulant development, advances the understanding of alkali-activated lunar construction materials and supports the development of sustainable technologies for long-term lunar habitation.

Acknowledgement: This study was carried out within the Space It Up project funded by the Italian Space Agency, ASI, and the Ministry of University and Research, MUR, under contract n. 2024-5-E.0 – CUP n. I53D24000060005. This work also contributes to the GLAMS Project (Geopolymers for Additive Manufacturing and Lunar Monitoring), funded by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), coordinated by CISAS – University of Padova. The tomographic work presented here has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101131765 (EXCITE2) for Transnational Access conducted at Utrecht University.

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